

Prophetic Critique of Empty Religion: A Theological Analysis of Amos 5:21-24 in the Nigerian Context

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Abstract

Amos 5:21-24 depicts one of the most forceful prophetic rebukes against religious hypocrisy in the Old Testament. Prophet Amos condemned Israel’s religious festivities and sacrifices as detestable before God because they are void of justice and righteousness. The thrust of this paper therefore, is to explore Amos’ critique of empty religion and draws parallels with the socio-religious climate of the contemporary Nigerian Society, where religious devotion thrive amidst widespread injustice, corruption, and exploitation of the poor. The aim of the paper is to engage in theological analysis of Amos 5:21-24 and evaluate its implications for contemporary Nigerian Christianity, particularly in addressing the disconnection between worship and ethical conduct. The paper adopts historical – exegetical approach to achieve its aim. The findings of this paper show that the message of Amos remains profoundly relevant to Nigerian Society today. The Prophet’s denunciation of worship without justice serves as a timely call to religious leaders and adherents to re- examine the content and expression of their faith. It also underscores the necessity for a religion that upholds justice, equity and accountability as integral part of true worship. The

paper concludes that reclaiming the prophetic traditions of ethical religion is essential for national transformation.

Keywords: *prophetic critique, empty religion, social justice, theological, nigerian society.*

1.0 Introduction

Amos 5: 21-24 presents a striking prophetic denunciation of Israel's religious life, where God rejected ritual practices devoid of justice and righteousness. In fact, the heart of Amos' message is the call to live in justice. He was a Prophet "par excellence" of social justice who always rebuked the Israelites on their hypocritical worship and sacrifices at the expense of justice and humanistic culture. The prophetic voice of Amos insists that the true worship must be accompanied with ethical conduct, and social justice.

In the contemporary Nigerian Society, the growth of religious worship exists side by side with the prevalent of corruption, injustice, and exploitations which is tantamount to religious apostasy. This paradox calls for critical, theological, and ethical enquiry about the relationship between authentic religious practices and social responsibility.

This article examines Amos 5: 21-24 as a prophetic denunciation of religiosity full of rituals, devoid of justice and righteousness, using it as a lens to critique the contemporary Nigerian religious landscape. The paper adopts historical – exegetical approach as the basis of discussion. The historical and critical analysis of Amos' text will enhance the critique of religious practices in Nigerian Society and assist in drawing a valid conclusion.

The paper has five major sections, namely: an overview of Amos' life and ministry, Scriptural review of Amos 5: 21-24, exegesis of Amos 5: 21-24, the Nigerian religious climate, and contextualization of Amos 5:21-24 to Nigerian society.

2.0 An Overview of Amos' Life and Ministry

The name Amos means "to carry load or a burden."¹ His name latter encapsulated the prophetic ministry he found himself in. This is due to the fact that the Prophet felt burdened by the combination of Israel's moral and social sins. Amos was one of the twelve Minor Prophets, a prophet of eighth century BC. He was a native of Tekoa, a town which is about twelve miles south

¹ E. Itapson and G. E . Janvier, A Study of the Major and Minor Prophets of the Old Testament (Kaduna: Prudent Universal Press, 2010),95.

of Jerusalem² He was neither a prophet nor a son of a prophet, but a herdsman and a dresser of sycamore trees before he was called to prophetic ministry (Amos 7:14). He prophesied in the days of Uzziah, king of Judah and Jeroboam the son of Joash, the king of Israel two years before the earthquake (Amos 1:1). Amos was undoubtedly an eloquent preacher whose message could not be ignored by his hearers.³ This is virtually true of this highly revered Prophet because his prophetic ministry to Israel in the eighth century BC provided a powerful prophetic witness for all ages.

Amos was the first of the prophets whose words of prophecy are preserved in the form of a book. He has always been admired for the purity of his language, his beauty of diction, and his poetic art. In all these respects, he is Isaiah's progenitor.⁴ He prophesied in the Northern Kingdom of Israel somewhere between 760-750 B.C in the midst of eighth century, a few years before prophet Hosea began his prophetic ministry. During the long reign of king Jeroboam II, the Northern kingdom of Israel enjoyed one of its most happy and prosperous periods. Together with the good political situation came economic prosperity which made many people in the Northern kingdom became very wealthy, and began to lead a luxurious life.⁵ Unfortunately, the unusual prosperity brought a collapse of moral standards in the nation. They ignore the great ideals and commandments of the Torah to help the poor and to practice justice and loving kindness. Although Amos lived in Tekoa, a small village bordering the wilderness of Judah, his preaching to Israel provided a powerful prophetic witness for all ages because of his condemnation of the spiritual blindness of the Judean upper class and their unjust exploitation of the poor. The ministry of Amos forged an explicit and unbreakable link between justice towards one's neighbour and righteousness before God. His ministry provides an eternal witness of God's opposition to economic, political and social injustice.⁶

Furthermore, during Amos' ministry, religion was gradually losing its hold; luxury and drunkenness were on the increase. Wealth was accumulating in fewer hands by open injustice. People became prodigal in their spending and therefore covetous. The small land owners were

² T. Adeyemo, Ed. "Amos" In African Bible Commentary (Nairobi Kenya: Zondervan Publishers, 2006), 1059.

³ E. Itapson and G. E. Janvier, 95.

⁴ E. Itapson and G. E. Janvier, 96.

⁵ Rick, R. Marris, "The World of the Eighth Century Prophets," Leaven no 2 (2008): 24.

⁶ M. S. Mignillat, Commentary on Amos 5: 21-24, in <http://www.workingpreacher.org>, accessed on 22/7/2025.

dispossessed by their rich neighbors and could not secure justice from courts presided over by corrupt judges. The picture of the national life was luxury for the privileged few and poverty for the masses.⁷ Although, Amos predicted a terrible day of judgment, his anxiety was not shared by the governing class, instead they maintained that no evil could come to them because they were God's chosen people and therefore secured no matter what they did. The time Amos ministered was a crucial time, and it was an age that needed a reformer and statesman. Amos fearlessly attacked these evils and warned the people of the inevitable collapse which would follow corruption.⁸ Amos' message to an oppressed society and his concern for the poor and the oppressed made him a Prophet for all times.

The main teachings of prophet Amos in his ministry are:

- i. Religious act that is against God's will is unacceptable in His sight.
- ii. Intimacy with Yahweh is requested rather than external form of worship.
- iii. Justice should be a lifestyle of a nation for the nation to prosper
- iv. Idolatry is forbidden by Yahweh.
- v. Good moral form the basis of good relationship with God.

The biblical evidence shows that the ministry of Prophet Amos spanned through the reigns of Uzziah, king of Judah (767-740/39 B.C.), and Jeroboam II of Israel (782/81-753 B.C.).⁹ Also, the Apocryphal work, *The Lives of the Prophets* records that Amos was killed by the son of Amaziah priest of Bethel. It further states that before he died, Amos made his way back to his homeland and was buried there.¹⁰

3.0 Scriptural Review

Scriptural review is an essential aspect of scholarly work in biblical and theological studies to substantiate current work. Jesus used this method in several places in the Bible.¹¹ To follow Jesus

⁷ Ibid.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ T. E. McComiskey, "Amos" In *Espositor' Bible Commentary*, ed. By Gaebelin et al. Vol 17 (Grand Rapids: Zondervan Publishing House, 1985), 320.

¹⁰ Ibid., 321.

¹¹ See Ilesanmi, Dele "Steps Involved in Utilising Scriptural Review Research Methods as a Tool for Explaining Biblical Research Problems" and "The Imperative of Scriptural Review in Biblical

model as asserted by Ilesanmi (2025),¹² this section gives a scriptural review of Amos 5:21-24 to validate the author's argument. Amos 5:21–24 presents one of the most profound theological critiques of Israel's cultic practices. The passage underscores God's rejection of empty ritualism and asserts that authentic worship cannot be divorced from ethical responsibility. Theologically, Amos situates true religion within the framework of covenantal fidelity, where justice (*mishpat*) and righteousness (*tsedaqah*) are central expressions of Israel's relationship with Yahweh. Worship devoid of ethical commitment, therefore, becomes a distortion of the covenant.

This prophetic stance is not isolated but resonates across the canon. Isaiah 1:11–17 demonstrates the same tension between sacrificial worship and moral conduct, where God rejects blood sacrifices while demanding justice for the oppressed. Similarly, Micah 6:8 distills covenant obligations into a triadic formula: to do justice, to love kindness, and to walk humbly with God. Theologically, this text emphasizes that God's requirements transcend ceremonial observances and call for holistic obedience.

In addition, Jeremiah 22:3 applies this covenantal ethic particularly to rulers, insisting on justice and deliverance for the oppressed as an outworking of divine kingship. Hosea 6:6 further intensifies this theological trajectory by declaring God's delight in *hesed* (steadfast love) and the knowledge of God rather than burnt offerings. Here, worship is redefined as relational fidelity rather than ritual performance.

Wisdom literature supports this prophetic critique. Proverbs 15:8 declares that the sacrifice of the wicked is an abomination to the Lord, contrasting it with the prayer of the upright, thereby grounding worship in moral integrity. The New Testament continues this theological continuity. In Matthew 23:23, Jesus exposes the Pharisees' misplacement of priorities, upholding justice, mercy, and faithfulness as the weightier matters of the Law, thus aligning Himself with the prophetic tradition.

Research Studies: A Proposal for Paradigm Shift from Literature Review” in *Mature Journal of International Institute of Christian theologians, Scholars, and Professionals*, 2025.

¹² Ibid.

Theologically, these scriptural witnesses converge to reveal a God whose nature prioritizes ethical transformation over ceremonial compliance. They portray worship as a covenantal act that integrates cult and conduct, ritual and righteousness. Amos and the prophetic corpus, therefore, call not merely for liturgical reform but for a reorientation of the heart—a transformation that embodies God’s justice and righteousness in every dimension of life.

4.0 Exegesis of Amos 5:21-24

1.4.1 Text and Translation of Amos 5:21 – 24

21. sane’ti ma’as^etti haggekem

22. ki’im-ta’alu-li ’olotumin^e hotekem lo’ ‘er^esh w^eselem m^eri’ ekem lo’ ‘abbi.

23. haser me’alay hamon sireyka w^ezim^eratn^e baleyka lo’ ‘es^ema’.

24. w^eyiggal kammayim mis^eppat us^edaqah k^enabal ‘etan. (Transliteration in Hebrew)

1.4.2 Translation of Amos 5:21-24

21 I hate, I despise your feasts, and take no delight in your solemn assemblies.

22 Even though you offer me your burnt offerings and cereal offerings, I will not accept them, and the peace offerings of your fatted beasts, I will not look upon.

23 Take away from me the noise of your songs; to the melody of your harps I will not listen.

24 But let justice roll down like waters, and righteousness like an overflowing stream. (RSV)¹³

4.1 Syntactical Analysis of Amos 5:21 – 24

¹³See the Revised Standard Translation of the Bible.

This section examines the syntax and grammatical analysis of the passage generally. It considers the structure of sentences, clauses and phrases to be able to reveal the intention of the text. It also looked at the syntactical harmony of the words and their functions and how it affects the meaning and interpretations of the passage. This analysis will be done verse by verse.

Verse 21:

sane'ti ma'as^etti haggekem welo'ariha be'ass^erolekem.

Translation: I hate, I despise your religious feasts; I cannot stand your assemblies. (Translation in English Bible)

sane'ti ma'as^etti (I Hate and I Despise) are two strong words God used to describe His feelings for the Israelites in this verse. Such strong words used are meant to impress upon the people the revulsion with which Yahweh viewed their religious activities. The two verbs juxtaposed asyndetically in first person address with “your feast” as object. God said He hated and despised their religious feasts. There are some religious feasts that the Israelites participated in annually e.g. festival of the unleavened bread, Passover, festival of weeks, Harvest and festival of tabernacle. These were the feasts that God was referring to.

The Hebrew word for hate is *sane'ti* used three times in the book of Amos; it means in Qal perfect, to hate or to be hateful. It can be used of man or for God. In Niphal, it means to be hated, and in Piel it means hater. It can be used of a person, nation, God or wisdom.¹⁴ Yahweh is rarely said to hate people (Hos. 9:15; Mal.1:13; Ps. 11:5; 31:7); things or abstract qualities are more often the object of God's hatred (Isa. 61:8; Jer. 44:4; Deut. 12:31; Zech 8:17). This shows Yahweh's hatred of their religious observance and all their feasts were not pleasing to Him because the people lacked the love, concern and humble obedience to God that marks sincere profession of faith.

The phrase “I despise”, in Hebrew is (*ma'as^etti*) which is a synonym of the word abhor. In Qal perfect it means to reject, to despise or to refuse. In Niphal it means to be rejected to flow or to run.¹⁵ God told them that He cannot stand their assemblies. The Hebrew noun (*'atsarah*), which literally means to smell, to perceive odour or to accept is used to express God's feeling concerning

¹⁴ T. E. McComiskey, “Amos” in Expository Bible Commentary, 321.

¹⁵ Mare, Z. Brettlee, “Amos” in the Jewish Study Bible. Adele Berlin et al. Eds. (New York: Oxford University Press, 2004), 605.

their religious assemblies. It can be used of a horse or used metaphorically to delight in something.¹⁶This is what God thought of their assemblies – they smell horrible.

Verse 22: ki'im-ta'alu-li
'olotumin^e hotekem lo'
'er^esh w^eselem m^eri' ekem
lo' 'abbit.

Translation: Even though you bring me burnt offerings and grain offerings, I will not accept them. Though you bring choice fellowship offerings, I will have no regard for them.

The repetition of the second person plural pronominal suffix reinforces the rejection: “even though you bring me burnt offering and grain offering, I (Yahweh) will not accept them.” The text clearly distinguishes the action of the audience from the reaction of the speaker via its use of such grammatical devices. There are three of the five main Levitical offerings that are in this passage (Lev. 1:7) in Leviticus, these three main offerings were a pleasing aroma to the Lord as they represented consecration and worship.¹⁷The other two offerings – sin and guilt were used for atonement. The two verbs used in this verse help in determining the meaning of the unit as a whole. The first, *lo' 'eresh* “I will not accept,” is the ordinary and most frequently used for the acceptance or rejection of a sacrificial gift. The root 'er^esh is frequently used in Leviticus when the priests, the officiating ministers of the sacrifice, declares whether an animal of sacrifice or some specific ritual action associated with ritual is or is not acknowledge by Yahweh.

A major difference between the priestly use of the verb in Leviticus and Yahweh's use of it in Amos is that, while the priest issues a ruling on an individual gift, animal, or prayer, Yahweh rejects Israel's entire ritual activity and He does so using traditional cultic vocabulary. The second verb used is, *lo' 'abbit*, “I will not look upon” this verb has a connotation of not accepting or to despise. The Lord despised the offerings being presented by the Israelites. The Hebrew word for regard is 'abbit, in Piel and Hiphil it means to look, to regard, to show regard, to pay attention, to look upon or to consider.¹⁸The word here is used in a figurative sense to represent a spiritual and inner

¹⁶ Ibid., 606.

¹⁷ T. E. McComiskey, 321.

¹⁸ Mare, Z. Brettler, “Amos” in the Jewish Study Bible, 606.

looking. The Lord refused to look, show regard or pay attention to the offerings of the Israelites because they did not incorporate the act of mercy into their religious activities.

Verse 23:

haser me'alay hamon sireyka w^ezim^eratn^e baleyka lo' 'es^ema'

Translation: Away with the noise of your songs! I will not listen to the music of your harps.

Harp is an important musical instrument Israelites played while singing praises to the Lord. The playing of harp appears to have been part of the official trappings of Israel cultic life. Harps therefore are instruments that accompany both worship and divine speech.¹⁹ Harps are not only played during worship, but also influence prophetic inspiration by which God will speak through a prophet to the nation. Yahweh's command to the people *me'alay*, "away" or "take away" in Qal perfect, it means to take away or to carry off. The Lord was telling the Israelites to take away their worship and labeled their songs as noise. The singing of their Psalms is nothing but a wearisome noise before God. To remove their music and singing from him suggests that the weight their songs and music are heavy objects that are burden to him. The first object used, *sireyka*, "your songs" appears with the singular masculine construct noun modifier *hamon*, "noisy."²⁰ It indicates that their songs have become a noise in the ears of Yahweh. The sound of singing that the people associated with liturgical worship is ill – received by Yahweh who instructs them to cease that activity.

Verse 24:

w^eyiggal kammayim mis^eppat us^edaqah k^enabal 'etan.

Translation: But let justice roll on like a river, righteousness like a never-failing stream!

This verse contains the dominant theme of Amos' message. The conjunctive *waw* that begins the clause when it precedes a jussive verb expresses contrast, "but," because the following positive

¹⁹ Silas, B. Akande, *The Relevance of Eighth Century Prophecy to Socio-Religious Challenges in Southwest Nigeria*, 70.

²⁰ F. Brown, S. R. Driver, and C. A. Briggs, *A Hebrew and English Lexicon of the Old Testament Theology and Exegesis*, ed. By W. A. Vangemeren (Grand Rapids Michigan: Zondervan Publishers, 1980), 744.

clause reverses the tone set by the negative clauses of vv. 21-23. It is a command by Yahweh to the people of Israel to take a specific action. Two words are the heart of the message in this verse, i.e. *mis^eppat us^edaqah* (justice and righteousness). The word justice in Hebrew is (*mis^eppat*) and it indicates a verdict whether favourable or unfavourable. It also indicates right or privilege.²¹ The word justice, as used in the verse is a singular masculine noun which means a judgment, a legal decision, a legal case, a claim, proper or rectitude.²⁰ Obviously, the word is diverse in meaning depending on the context of usage. It is used to describe a legal decision given by God to be followed by the people (Isa. 58: 2). It was this virtue of justice that the Lord was expecting from the nation of Israel before their worship could be acceptable to Him.

Furthermore, the second word, righteousness can be used as a verb, as a Noun, and as an adjective. In the verb form connotes to be in the right path, to be justified, or to be just. It occurs fewer than 40 times in the Biblical Hebrew. It is a legal term which involves the whole process of justice. It may also be used to signify the outcome of a verdict, when a man is pronounced just and judicially cleared of all charges. In the Noun form, it signifies alms or demonstration of mercy. The two Hebrew words are legal terms signifying justice in conformity with the legal corpus. In the Adjective form, the word righteousness is *tsaddiq*, meaning righteous or just. It signifies loyalty in the old Aramaic. The word righteousness connotes blameless conduct and integrity. It describes justice, right actions and right attitudes. The word is also synonymous with truth.²¹ The Lord was expecting the Israelites to maintain righteousness before their worship gain acceptance before Him.

The Lord's rejection of Israel's religious activities was due to their rejection of justice and righteousness dealing with the social concern of their days. This would be an outward sign of their religious devotion unto God. The element that will transform the people's sterile worship into worship acceptable to God is justice and righteousness.²² Yahweh's expectation from the Israelites is presented as a pair of simile: *kammayim mis^eppat us^edaqah k^enabal 'etan*, justice is to roll on like a river and righteousness like a never failing stream – this is one of the great similes in the Old Testament which indicates a continuous flow of justice and righteousness. A momentary flow of these virtues will not do, but these virtues are to keep on in the social order like a stream that does not dry up in the summer heat.²³ All Israel's feasts, assemblies, offerings, and music are to flow

²¹ R. D. Culver, "mispahat". In the Theological Workbook of Old Testament, vol 11, ed. By R. L. Harris et al. (Chicago: Moody Press, 1981): 948.

out of the consistent practice of justice and righteousness within the community. The interaction between justice and righteousness comes to life when justice is seen as what needs to be done in a given situation if people and circumstances are to be restored to conformity with righteousness. When Yahweh demanded justice and righteousness from the people of Israel, He wanted them to actually remove violence and stop their extortion of the poor and vulnerable (Ezek. 45:9). Thus, when properly executed by the total elimination of exploitation and oppression, the product is social justice. Justice and righteousness represents acts done on behalf of the poor and it implies the deliverance of the weak and vulnerable from vulnerability and weakness by the elimination of oppression and exploitation that can inhibit their progress.²²

In the expectation of Yahweh, justice and righteousness in people's lives, hospitality towards their neighbours, right judgments at the city gates, proper weights and measures in the markets are far more important than offering and unneeded sacrifice. (Prov. 21:3). Therefore, for their worship to gain acceptance, true sign of repentance must be seen in their midst i.e. justice and righteousness must roll down like a river and like a mighty stream. This means that justice and righteousness must be a continuous attitude among them. They should form a perpetual lifestyle of justice and righteousness.

4.2 Exegetical Inference and Interpretation of Amos 5: 21-24

From the exegetical interpretation of the passage, the following inference can be drawn from the passage: First, religious activities should reflect good moral life. Israel's act of worship was rejected due to their uncared attitude towards the poor. Israelites of the eighth century were religious, but their religion was not positively reflected on their moral life. Their worship was characterized by offering and sacrifices made in the temple, but void of act of piety. However, all the religious practices of the people were rejected because they were not attached to matters of justice and righteousness as a prerequisite to accepted worship.

Secondly, God cannot be deceived with religious activities. The Israelites thought within themselves that they could use offerings and sacrifices to secure God's favour at the expense of maltreating the poor. God cannot be deceived; whatsoever a man sows he will reap (Gal. 6: 7).

²²D. J. Reimer, *The New International Dictionary of Old Testament Theology and Exegesis*, ed. By W. A. Vangemeren, (Grand Rapids Michigan: Zondervan Publishers, 1980), 744.

God is not only looking at what one does but also the heart of the doer. God is not a respecter of any person, religious activities are good, but for one's religious activities to be accepted by God, it has to be corroborated with the act of piety.

Furthermore, it is inferred from the passage that God has so much interest in the poor and the needy. The poor and the needy are at the peak of the agenda of God, in fact, God personally fight for them. (Psa. 82:3; 82:4; Jer. 22:16). In the book of Deuteronomy, God Himself knew that the poor and the needy shall not cease from the land so, He commanded the Israelites not to oppress them but to care for them (Deut. 15:11; 24:14). The rejection of the offerings and sacrifices of the Israelites was due to the inhuman attitude towards the poor and the needy.

5.0 Contextualization of Amos' Message to Nigerian Society

Nigeria boasts of having the highest Church attendances globally due to proliferation of churches all over the country. However, this religiosity has not translated into ethical governance or social equity. Corruption persists, and Churches often serve as platform for wealth display and political alliance. Like ancient Israel, Nigerian society exhibit spiritual activities devoid of ethical transformation whereby worship is vibrant, but justice is absent.

Furthermore, Nigeria is a multi-religious nation with proliferation of places of worship especially churches but not rooted in the virtues of justice and righteousness. Righteousness is a virtue that is essential to the well – being of the community. Righteousness has to do with the relationship between a person and God, as well as relationship between members of the community. Nigeria is littered with Churches, virtually every street one will find more than four different Church denominations, but justice and righteousness are missing in religious activities like the Israelites during Amos' time. It is good to be religious, but religion without moral standard is not acceptable to God. Israelites were vast in the observance of their religious activities and the popular and official religion was at its best while the participants were decayed morally.²³ This made God to reject their worship and demanded repentance from them. Corruption in the contemporary Nigerian society extends to Churches, and the church wrongly holds that performing religious

²³ M. I. Okwueze, *The Old Testament as History, Religion and Literature*, (Nsukka: AP Express Publishers, 2001), 151- 152.

rituals is sufficient to satisfy God.²⁴ Religious leaders should emphasize more on the need for righteousness in all religious activities. However, no amount of outward religion will impress God, if it is not rooted in obedience to God's commandments. The message of Amos compels Nigerian Christianity to embrace holistic worship – one rooted in both reference for God and justice for humanity. Thus, the only thing Nigeria need in her religious life is complete repentance like Amos' time, "let justice roll down like a river and righteousness as an ever dry stream".

6.0 Conclusion and Recommendation

This paper had looked into the Prophetic critique of empty religion, using the message of Amos in Amos 5: 21-24 as the basis of discussion. The message was contextualized to Nigerian Society; exegesis of the text, Amos 5:21-24 was done in order to further enhance the understanding of the message and the requirements of God from the Israelites which is also relevant to the Nigerian society. During the ministry of Amos in the eighth century BC, there was economic prosperity and this creates a wide gap between the rich and the poor. People were either very rich or very poor. Sadly, some of the wealth of the rich came about because the poor have been deprived of basic necessities of life. The judiciary was perverted and the poor cannot find redress in the court of law because of bribes. Religious activities were also observed without moral standard. Amos 5: 21-24 stands as a timeless prophetic critique of empty religion, and it is very relevant to the Nigerian context, where performative worship coexist with moral and social decline. God desire not only in songs and offerings alone, but also in justice and righteousness. This paper discovered that religion and morality are two sides of a coin. Also, it is discovered from Amos 5: 21-24 that religious activities without justice are abominable and unacceptable to God. The virtue of justice and righteousness should not be intermittent, but a way of life.

Therefore, it is evident from this paper that the experiences during the time of Amos and those of contemporary Nigerian society bear striking similarities. While worship is vibrant and religious activities abound, the essential demands of justice and righteousness remain neglected. On a final note, this study recommends that religious leaders intensify their teaching and advocacy on justice and righteousness as indispensable prerequisites for true and acceptable worship. Religious institutions, especially churches, should also place greater emphasis on morality and ethical living

²⁴ Timothy Agboluaje, "The Ministry of Amos in Israel and its Socio- Religious Implications for the Nigerian Nation", *Biblical Studies and Corruption in Africa*, 6 (2007): 175.

as integral to their liturgical life. Ultimately, the reformation of Nigerian religious practice must begin with a sincere return to the prophetic vision that upholds justice and righteousness as the true essence of worship.

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